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Hydrodynamic real-time hybrid simulation to examine aero-hydro-structural-soil dynamics of offshore monopile wind turbines

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Abstract

Offshore wind turbines (OWTs) are expected to play a major role in the energy transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy. However, OWTs are subjected to complex dynamic forces due to combined wind and wave loading, along with soil-structure interaction effects. Due to incompatibilities in simulating multiple dynamic forces simultaneously at model scale, conventional experimental approaches are limited in simulating the response of the wind turbines subjected to combined aero- and hydro-dynamic forces interacting with soil-structural dynamics. Real-time hybrid simulation (RTHS) is a numerical-physical simulation approach that can alleviate similitude limitations by partitioning the system dynamics into physical and numerical subassemblies that interact through sensors and actuators in real time. A hydrodynamic RTHS framework, hydro-RTHS, is presented to simulate the response of a monopile OWT subjected to simultaneous wind and wave loading. The system was partitioned such that: [a] the hydrodynamics on the tower were modeled physically at model scale and [b] the remaining dynamics, including aerodynamics, structural dynamics, and soil effects, were modeled numerically at full scale. Wind forces applied at the hub were pre-simulated and applied to the numerical soil-structure model. Force feedback from the pre-determined wind loading and measured physical wave loading was used in the governing equations to calculate command displacements, which were physically applied using an actuator and virtually applied in the numerical soil-structure model. Geometry, time, and forces used to actuate and measure the physical model were scaled via Froude scaling to more realistically represent the hydrodynamic forces in the governing equations. Results demonstrate that the hydro-RTHS can simulate combined aero-hydro-structural-soil response of monopile OWT, which cannot be obtained using conventional approaches with distorted similitude effects.

Keywords: monopile offshore wind turbines; real-time hybrid simulation;

1. Introduction

Offshore wind turbines (OWTs) can access largely untapped offshore wind resources; thus, OWTs are expected to play a major role in the energy transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy. Although promising in terms of steadier and more reliable wind, the offshore environment also introduces complex dynamic forces acting on OWTs due to

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combined wind and wave loading interacting with the structure. Additionally, the structural dynamics of monopile wind turbines are subject to soil effects, which, combined with the many interacting dynamics, is difficult to simulate in model-scale experimental tests.

Experimental studies including multiple dynamic forces, such as coupled hydro- or aero-dynamic forces interacting with structural dynamics and soil, are often limited due to spatial and capacity constraints in hydro- or aero-dynamic facilities [1]. Thus, model-scale or full-scale component tests are the status quo. Such tests cannot simulate the response of complete systems at full scale and are subject to distorted similitude for systems subject to multiple dynamic forces.

Developing other approaches to simulate the response of OWTs would advance understanding of their dynamic response and loads, thereby improving the mid-fidelity modeling and design of OWTs needed in industry. Real-time hybrid simulation (RTHS) is a testing method that can alleviate the aforementioned limitations by coupling numerical and physical simulations through the governing equations of motion. The RTHS approach was previously developed to examine seismic response of structures [2] and has recently been used to investigate fluid-structure interaction [3].

This paper illustrates an application of hydrodynamic RTHS (hydro-RTHS) to examine the response of a monopile wind turbine subjected to simultaneous wave and wind loading. The aero-hydro-structural-soil system was partitioned into a physical subassembly consisting of physical waves and a model-scale specimen representing the tower and a full-scale numerical subassembly representing the remaining structure, its dynamics, soil effects, and wind loading in the structural analysis framework, OpenSEES [4]. The wind forces were pre-calculated prior to the experiments using NREL's OpenFAST. Using the hydro-RTHS approach, experiments in the wave flume can be virtually extended to mitigate similitude distortion and include multiple forces acting simultaneously on OWTs.

2. Hydro-RTHS methodology

Fig. 1(a) shows the 5-MW monopile OWT simulated in Phases I-II in the OC3 project [5]. The tower was linearly tapered across the height; the diameter and thickness were 6 m and 0.027 m at the base and 3.87 m and 0.019 m at the top, respectively. The diameter of the monopile was also 6 m. Young's modulus of the steel was 2.1×10^8 kN/m². The monopile was fixed at the foundation in Phase I but included soil-structure interaction in Phase II.

Fig. 1. Model for RTHS:(a) 5-MW monopile offshore wind turbine (OC3); (b) physical subassembly; (c) numerical subassembly

2.1. Physical and numerical subassemblies

The complete system shown in Fig. 1(a) was partitioned into physical and numerical subassemblies (see Fig. 1(b) and (c)). Hydrodynamics were physically modeled using waves and a cylindrical column in the Large Wave Flume at the O.H. Hinsdale Wave Research Laboratory at Oregon State University. The 0.51-m diameter cylindrical column was supported by a pin at the base. At 3-m height from the pin support, displacements were controlled by an actuator, where forces due to the wave were also measured using a load cell at the same location. The ratio of the diameters of the monopile at full scale, 6 m, to the cylindrical column, 0.51 m, determined the length scale $\lambda_L = 11.8$ between the physical and numerical subassemblies.

The numerical subassembly was modeled at full scale in OpenSEES and included the structural dynamics of the tower, pre-simulated wind forces at the hub, and soil effects. The remainder of the tower was equally discretized into 10 elastic beam-column elements representing the tower taper at midspan of the element. Mass was lumped at the nodes located at the ends of each element of the tower, with a larger lumped mass located at the hub representing the

mass of the nacelle and blades.

To consider soil effects in select test cases, a rotational soil-structure interaction (SSI) spring was utilized at the base of the monopile with rotational stiffness condensed from the stiffness matrix of the monopile foundation [6]. The bilinear spring was calibrated using [7]. Translational and vertical springs were not considered for soil effects as the physical specimen was restrained by the pin in these directions; note, the translational degree-of-freedom of the soil likely has the most influence on the wave loading. The element representing the cylindrical column in the physical subassembly was represented using an elastic, stiff element; modeling the experimental portion of the tower in this fashion ensured that the reactions of the pinned cylindrical specimen and the rotational soil spring were consistent.

The aerodynamic force history applied to the structural hub location was pre-simulated using OpenFAST with 21 m/s dynamic wind input assuming rigid structural properties and with still water. Future applications of hydro-RTHS can consider structural displacements to inform the aerodynamic loading, but those were not considered herein.

2.2. Laboratory setup

Fig. 2 shows the test setup for the physical subassembly. The depth of water was 2.74 m from the flume floor to the still water level (SWL) and 1.69 m from the ramped-up floor to the SWL near the physical subassembly. An actuator, load cell, and LVDT were attached to the cylinder at 3 m above the pin support. A load cell was also located at the pinned base. The cylinder was laterally braced near the top. A wave height of 0.88 m and wave period of 4.2 s were used for all trial runs, corresponding to a 10.4 m height and 14.4 s period at full scale.

Fig. 2. Test setup for physical sub assembly

2.3. Synchronizing the physical-numerical subassemblies

The length, force, and time scales were synchronized between the numerical and physical subassemblies using Froude similitude. The three-loop-hardware RTHS architecture [8] consisted of: (1) a *host* machine housing the numerical subassembly, including the finite-element analysis of the numerical soil-structure model and predetermined wind forces; (2) the *target* machine housing extrapolation-interpolation [9] and scaling algorithms to synchronize the numerical model to the physical model; (3) the controller and data acquisition (DAQ) machine that controls the actuator and receives the measured signals from the sensors. Each machine exchanges information using a low latency shared memory ring, SCRAMNet GT. Fig. 3 shows the machine communication including scaling for length and force. The extrapolation and interpolation algorithm handles the time scaling.

Hydrodynamic forces measured from the physical assembly and aerodynamic forces pre-determined from OpenFAST informed the state of the numerical soil-structure model, which was integrated in time to calculate command displacements actuated on the physical subassembly at the next time step. Displacements at each degree-of-freedom for the next time step were computed by solving the equations of motion of the numerical soil-structure model, as shown in Fig. 3 **Error! Reference source not found.**, with inputs from the numerical wind loading, F^{i+1} , and scaled-up measured forces due to the waves, f_{fbk}^{i+1} . The displacement corresponding to the node controlled by the

Fig. 3. Machine communication with Froude scaling in displacement, force and time

actuator in the physical subassembly, x_{sim} , was sent to the target machine, which was then scaled down by dividing by λ_L to attain the command displacement x_{comm} to be sent to the controller and actuator. The hydrodynamic force due to the waves measured using the load cell, f_{meas} , was sent to the target machine, which was scaled up by multiplying by λ_L^3 as feedback to the numerical subassembly as f_{fbk}^{i+1} .

The host machine solving the equations of motion may solve a time step at a different rate than that needed for the controller, which is deterministic with rate Δt_{con} . To synchronize the numerical subassembly with a physical subassembly, the target PC sends f_{fbk} from the DAQ to the host PC. OpenSees then needs to solve the equation of motions with timing matched to the physical sub-assembly. OpenFresco [9] uses a flag to tell OpenSees to hold on solving the equation of motion for the next time step until the time increases by Δt_{sim} in real time so that the numerical subassembly advances one integration time step Δt_{int} every Δt_{sim} . By Froude scaling, Δt_{sim} was shrunk by $\sqrt{\lambda_L}$ so that full-scale real-time was matched to the small-scale time in the experiment. To maintain continuous control, the target PC also needs to send x_{comm} to the controller every Δt_{con} smaller than Δt_{sim} . The gap in sample rate was filled by the extrapolation-interpolation algorithm [9].

3. Results

Results were compared with and without hydro-RTHS, including the structural dynamics with and without the aerodynamics. Additionally, comparisons included fixed versus soil-spring models at the base of the monopile. In Case 1, the actuator was held at the initial position to represent a near-rigid structure with only hydrodynamic loading. In Case 2, the numerical subassembly used for hydro-RTHS only included the structural dynamics without the wind forces. In Case 3, pre-simulated wind forces were included in the numerical subassembly in addition to the structural dynamics; thus, aero-hydro-structural dynamic effects were included in the test. In Case 4, the SSI spring was added at the base of the monopile (Cases 1-3 had a fixed base).

Fig. 4 compares moment histories for the fixed foundation. Higher-frequency dynamic effects due to the structural dynamics can be seen in the moment histories by comparing Cases 1 and 2. By considering forces due to wind, the moment history also exhibits large interacting effects, affecting the moments in Case 3. The maximum moments at the base in Case 1, 2, and 3 were 2.93×10^4 , 3.08×10^4 , 5.84×10^4 kNm, respectively, where the moment in Case 3 was 2.02 times larger than the maximum moment in Case 1 due to the hydrodynamic and aerodynamic forces superimposing during the experiment. Fig. 5 compares moment histories for Cases 3 and 4 with the yielding moment of the SSI spring. Both cases consider aero-hydro-structural dynamics but differ in terms of the base fixity. Introducing the SSI spring partially decreased the moment in Case 4 through inelastic soil behavior. The moment history in Case 4 differed from Case 3 as time passed and the nonlinear SSI spring exhibited greater inelastic effects.

Fig. 4. Moment history at fixed foundation

4. Discussions

Several characteristics of the hydro-RTHS tests could contaminate the results. First, in Cases 2-3, forces measured from the load cell and sent as feedback to the numerical subassembly included noise at frequencies outside of the relevant dynamics, affecting the command displacements outputted from the numerical subassembly and leading to numerical instabilities. The influence of this noise can be observed at ~ 80 s and 125 s in Case 2 in Fig 4. Subsequently, this feedback force was filtered by a low-pass filter at 10 Hz, resulting in more stable displacement commands.

Comparisons between Cases 1 and 2 also exhibit a lag due to the extrapolation-interpolation algorithm and distortion in the time scale. Since the controller is deterministic, the extrapolation-interpolation algorithm synchronizes time by counting the controller time step Δt_{con} to match the numerical simulation time step Δt_{sim} ; thus, Δt_{sim} must be the multiple of Δt_{con} .

The wave and wind loading contributed more to the system dynamics compared to the structural dynamics. However, since the wind forces were predetermined without inputs from the physical subassembly, the wind loading may be initialized at a different time than the timing of the wave loading, resulting in different superposition effects and some differences in Fig. 5. Adding feedback to the aerodynamic loading using the structural nodal displacements and restoring forces would enable better synchronization of both the wave and wind loading.

Fig. 5. Moment history at fixed and SSI spring foundation due to hydro-, structural, and aero-dynamics

5. Conclusions

This paper illustrates an application of hydro-RTHS to examine the response of a monopile OWT. Results showed the effects of including coupled aero-hydro-structural-soil dynamics on the monopile response, with the largest contributions to the dynamics coming from the combined aero-hydrodynamic loading. Discussion of limitations and their mitigation included the need to filter noisy measured signals, to synchronize temporal similitude to the controller, and future work to update the wind forces using online feedback from the structural dynamics. Results of hydro-RTHS tests like these can be used to virtually extend hydrodynamic facilities for more realistic and reliable testing of all the forces affecting monopile wind turbines, informing efficient prototyping and design of OWTs in industry.

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